

WHITE PAPER – High Energy Astrophysics and Cosmology

The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY: a Precursor for the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA)

Thematic Areas:

Formation and Evolution of Compact Objects

Cosmology and Fundamental Physics

Stars and Stellar Evolution

Galaxy Evolution

Astroparticles

Multi-Messenger Astronomy and Astrophysics

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1. Introduction

The Universe is populated by natural extreme particle accelerators, capable of imbuing more than 10^{20} eV in a single proton. These sources could be used as probes, by observing their extreme radiation shining in γ -rays, to investigate the still hidden answers to understand the deep laws of Nature at the highest energies. For the first time, Cherenkov instrumentation, like the upcoming Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) Observatory will make possible to address questions related to the detection of the quantum nature of the gravitational field, the measurement of effects coming from exotic particles (like ALPs) and to understand definitively where the most energetic Cosmic Rays are produced. CTA will consist of two large arrays of imaging atmospheric-Cherenkov telescopes (IACTs) to detect VHE γ -rays. These VHE γ -rays are observed via the Cherenkov light produced in particle showers generated when they interact in the Earth's atmosphere. Aside from deep technological improvements with regard to current IACT observatories, CTA will cover a wide energy range from 20 GeV to 300 TeV, which necessitates the use of **three different telescope sizes: referred to as Large-, Medium- and Small-Sized Telescopes (LSTs, MSTs and SSTs)**. The LSTs provide sensitivity at the lowest energies and SSTs at the highest. CTA will provide full-sky coverage via locations in both the Northern and Southern Hemispheres. CTA will be the world's largest and most-sensitive γ -ray observatory, and 31 countries, including Brazil, participate in the CTA Consortium [1] (see also WP of CTA, de Gouveia Dal Pino et al. 2019 [2]).

The CTA Management council has recently chosen the **ASTRI (Astrofisica con Specchi a Tecnologia Replicante Italiana) structure to be the design of the 70 SSTs that will compose the CTA**, among two other projects.

The ASTRI SST is a two-mirror telescope equipped with the so called ASTRI camera developed by a CTA team including Italian, Brazilian, and South African Institutions.

In the framework of a FAPESP Thematic Project 13/10559-5 (coordinated by E. M. de Gouveia Dal Pino, IAG-USP), the Brazilian SST party (named SST-BR) has obtained funding to participate in the construction of the **ASTRI prototype and a MINI-ARRAY of ASTRI SSTs**. The SST-BR group is sponsoring three of the nine MINI-ARRAY structures; South Africa one of them; and Italy the remaining telescopes of the array. The total amount obtained from FAPESP for this thematic project is 12.200.000,00 Reais (or ~ 4 MEuro in 2014).

The SST prototype was constructed in Sicily and is now operational.

The **ASTRI MINI-ARRAY (Figure 1) will be a precursor for CTA**, to be installed at the Observatorio del Teide, in Tenerife, starting operation in 2022, well before the CTA. It will provide a full functional complement of MAGIC and CTA North (which lacks of the

Small Size Telescopes and, for this reason, has just a limited sensitivity at very high gamma-ray energies). The ASTRI mini-array, thanks to its sensitivity especially at energies greater than 1 TeV, represents the key instrument to perform very soon a ground breaking achievement in the field of extreme gamma rays, up to 100 TeV and beyond.

The ASTRI CTA team foresees two phases, which are distinct but continuous: the pathfinder phase and a production phase of SSTs for CTA. The second phase is described in the CTA WP [2].

In the pathfinder phase, it is planned the implementation of the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY which is described in this document.

2. Key Science Goals and Objectives

The ASTRI mini-array will allow us to perform early CTA science studies, with likely solid detections during the first year of operation. In this respect, prominent sources such as extreme blazars (KUV 00311–1938), nearby well-known BL Lac objects (Mrk 501) and radio-galaxies (M 87), galactic pulsar wind nebulae (Crab Nebula, Vela-X), supernovae remnants (Vela-junior, RX J1713.7–3946), as well as the Galactic Center can be observed in a previously unexplored energy range. In particular, one aims to investigate phenomena as the electron acceleration and cooling, relativistic and non-relativistic shocks, the search for cosmic-ray (CR) PeVatrons, the study of the CR propagation, and the impact of the extragalactic background light on the spectra of the sources.

The ASTRI mini-array will operate when the present IACT systems, observing in a lower, but partly overlapping energy range, will still be active, allowing direct comparison of scientific data (spectra, light-curves, integral fluxes). Besides, fruitful synergies with HAWC, surveying a very large stripe of the northern sky, with pointed observations are also clearly foreseen. In summary, the ASTRI mini-array will allow us to carry out seminal studies on both Galactic and extra-Galactic sources, tackling frontier issues at the intersection of the fields of astrophysics, cosmology, particle physics and fundamental physics.

Figure 1. Artistic concept (not in scale) of the ASTRI mini-array.

Figure 2. Simulated configurations for the ASTRI mini-array.

Figure 3: Expected flux sensitivity for the ASTRI mini-array.

The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY will therefore, address a wide range of major questions in and beyond astrophysics. The topics to be addressed are essentially the same as those of

the highest energy range of CTA Science case (see [2, 3]). These can be grouped into 4 broad themes:

Galactic Science: From the Tenerife site the ASTRI mini-array will have the observational access to important portions of the Galactic plan, including the Cygnus region and the galactic bulge. Moreover, profiting of the novel high zenith angle technique first experimented with MAGIC (Mirzoyan et al. 2019), many galactic regions will be explored with a very enhanced flux sensitivity at high energies. PeVatrons will be important targets. For instance, Tycho's SNR is the best candidate as Pevatron and it is well accessible from Tenerife. Also, RX J1713.7–3946 is a young shell-like SNR which could be considered as an excellent laboratory to investigate the cosmic ray acceleration. The recent detection of this SNR by *Fermi-Lat* and the combined study with H.E.S.S. (Figure 3) shows that the high-energy and very high-energy (VHE) emission could be interpreted in the framework of a leptonic scenario. Nevertheless, the majority of current models adopt a spherical geometry, while it is known that the gas distribution around the SNR is inhomogeneous. A clumpy circumstellar medium (CSM) could produce a hadronic spectrum different from the prediction of a simple spherical model. A detailed comparison between the proton distribution in the CSM and the high-resolution gamma-ray image is therefore, a useful test of the hadronic scenario. The improved sensitivity and angular resolution of the mini-array at energy above 10 TeV with respect to the current IACTs will allow us to investigate the VHE emission in the different regions of this source, studying their spectra. Another important target includes gamma-ray sources produced by middle-age SNRs interacting with Molecular Clouds (MC). Several sources like W 28, W 30, W 51C and IC 443 can be observed by the mini-array in Tenerife with better spatial and energy resolution than what has been done before. PWN originate from the interaction of the relativistic wind of a pulsar with the surrounding medium and thus are excellent candidates for the study of particle acceleration and cooling in relativistic shocks. The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY will be able to survey several TeV-emitting PWN, like Vela-X and HESS J1825–137.

Extragalactic Science: The ASTRI mini-array will be extremely important to investigate the VHE emission from extragalactic sources as well and, in particular, blazars. They represent a particular class of active galactic nuclei whose relativistic jet is pointed toward the Earth. They are natural accelerators and, besides studying the physical processes, they can probe the laws of nature at energies that are not yet accessible in any accelerators humans can build. Their emission, especially in the band of VHE γ -rays, brings all the information needed to: (i) assess if Blazars are responsible for the most energetic component of the cosmic ray spectrum; (ii) study the properties of the light emitted by galaxies in the cosmic history; (iii) search for violations of the Lorentz Invariance at the Planck Scale, at energies of many tens of TeV, in a complementary approach to the ones feasible within terrestrial laboratories.; and (iv) determine if

exotic particles, like Axion Like Particles (ALPs) exist. In order to gain insight of these answers, γ -rays photons from these cosmic sources must be measured and the more energetic they are, the more is the information carried. In particular, detecting events at energy greater than 10-20 TeV – as enabled by the ASTRI mini-array - will be the smoking gun that allows us to disentangle between pure leptonic emission from the jet or a mixture of hadrons. A potential target is the extreme blazar (E-HBL) 1ES 0229+200.

A clear detection of VHE emission above a few tens of TeV from such a blazar could provide a striking evidence for non-standard phenomena, either an anomalous transparency of the Universe at these energies or gamma-ray emission resulting from an electromagnetic cascade initiated by ultra-relativistic protons accelerated in the blazar jet and beamed toward the observer. In this respect, extragalactic VHE sources also act a unique role of cosmic probes. For instance, the interaction of the beams of particles and photons generated in the sources with the intergalactic environment along the line of sight to the observer, engraves in the observed radiation unique information on the density of the Extragalactic Background Light (EBL) generated by stars mainly in the optical band and reprocessed by dust in the infrared, and of its evolution across cosmic ages. This indirect information, independent from standard direct measurements based on direct methods such as galaxy counts, allows us to put tight constraints on the galaxy evolution models at intermediate redshifts. Some tensions between this method and the lower limits on EBL density put by galaxy counts, arose in the last years, as the Universe seems to be more transparent to VHE photons than expected. If confirmed, this phenomenon may hint to the existence of new particles such as axion-like particles. The field is evidently grazing issues of the utmost scientific interest, at the intersection of astrophysics, cosmology and fundamental physics.

The field is evidently grazing issues of the utmost scientific interest, at the intersection of astrophysics, cosmology and fundamental physics. In fact, the Universe is populated by extreme particle accelerators capable of imbuing more than 10^{20} eV in a single nucleus that act as a unique natural laboratory where the laws of physics can be proven in an energy range and on time and distance scales that are unachievable in any other context. This can provide compelling constraints that are both complementary and in competition with other methods, for instance for enquiring how quantum mechanics and relativity can be blended together at the Planck scale. The study of the EBL could be then be an important task for the MINI-ARRAY. Theory of quantum gravity predicts that γ -rays photons (especially at energies beyond few tens of TeV) experience a modified opacity from γ - γ absorption when interacting with EBL. Thus, if these effects are present, Blazars at $z > 0.2$ should evince excesses of flux for energies greater than few TeV. Possible candidates to perform this kind of studies should be nearby, hard, intense blazars. Among those observable from Tenerife, we

can consider MKN 421 ($z = 0.03$) and possibly M 87 ($z = 0.0043$), the latter one being less intense than the former. MKN 421 and M 87 will be observable from the CTA southern site at high zenith-angles, requiring ad-hoc Monte Carlo simulations in order to fully study their VHE properties. If detected above 10 TeV, M 87 would be particularly important to investigate the VHE emission mechanisms in radio-galaxies. Observations of MKN 421 above 10 TeV could be crucial, especially during high or very-high states, not only for the EBL studies, but also for the intrinsic relevance of this source. These observations will allow us to investigate the intra-night variability of such intense and low-redshift class of objects above a few TeV during periods of high-flux states.

Fundamental Physics Studies: The possibility to explore the most energetic part of the electromagnetic spectrum in the range 4 TeV – 300 TeV **for the first time** with IACT antennas by means of the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY opens new scenarios not only for astrophysical topics, but also for fundamental physics. In the same band, large shower detector arrays (e.g. HAWC or LHAASO) won't be able to go beyond a few detections with limited signal to noise ratio, because these wide FoV instruments cannot follow sources in deep targeted observations; therefore the availability of the ASTRI mini-array will be the crucial instrument to answer **a few main ground breaking questions** related to fundamental physics, as the search of axion-like particles or the search for quantum gravity effect in very high energy gamma-rays:

Do axion like particle exist? Axion Like Particles (ALPs, hereafter **a**) are a generalization of axions, that were proposed to solve the strong CP problem, in which the mass m and the $a\text{-}\gamma\gamma$ coupling constant are unrelated parameters. Direct detection of these particles is extremely difficult due to the very small coupling constant and the only available upper limit to the mass has been set from the CAST experiment to $m_a < 0.02$ eV. However, according to the Lagrangian density that describes interaction between ALPs and the ambient magnetic field **B**, an oscillation between γ and a ($\gamma \rightarrow a$) could take place. From an Astrophysics point of view, this translates directly into **opacity anomalies** in the high energy tail of the emission of distant ($z > 0.5$) blazars. When a γ -ray photon produced in the jet interacts with an external magnetic field (e.g. the extragalactic one) a conversion $\gamma \rightarrow a$ could take place. The ALP is then able to travel to the Earth unaffected by the presence of EBL, which diminishes the γ -ray flux proportionally to the distance of the source and to the energy of the photons. When the converted ALP encounters the magnetic field of the Milky-way in its journey toward the Earth it may be reconverted again into a γ -ray photon ($a \rightarrow \gamma$). This kind of process could in principle extend the γ -rays Cosmic Horizon far beyond $z > 0.5$ and, although a number of attempting measurements has been proposed, no significant and conclusive detection has been drawn so far. To answer this question, we plan to observe with the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY a sample of $z > 0.5$ blazars aiming to detect in the **unprobed** energy range 2 TeV – 100 TeV an excess of counts due to $\gamma \rightarrow a$ conversion.

This answer could only be tackled in synergy with study of EBL (previous point) that must be known precisely in order to detect these opacity anomalies.

Is there any quantum gravity effect visible in high energy gamma-rays? Theory of quantum gravity predicts that γ -rays photons (especially at energy beyond few tens of TeV) experience a modified opacity from γ - γ absorption when interacting with EBL. Thus, if these effects are present, Blazars at $z > 0.2$ should evince excesses of flux for energies greater than few TeV. We plan to select targets for which one will secure high quality spectra in the range 2 TeV – 100 TeV to be observed with the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY from Tenerife, aiming at detecting signatures from quantum gravity by exploring possible unexpected emission beyond few tens of TeV at and giving **for the first time** a direct test of the quantum nature of the gravitational field. The synergies between the characterization of EBL and detection of possible existence of ALPs is crucial to disentangle these three different effects.

Radiography with muons of the teide: With a recent patent, INAF has shown that the technologies in the framework of ASTRI, lend themselves to the realization of particular cameras capable to carry out real radiographs and / or tomographies of complex geological and tectonic structures of large dimensions. For example, in the case of volcanoes, information can be obtained with an unprecedented detail of the geometric characteristics of the conducts and the surface accumulation zones, improving the predictions on the volcano's activity status and consequently mitigating the risk linked to the occurrence of paroxysmal events. The muography is a similar technique in principle to radiography, which we all know. The substantial difference between radiography and muography lies in the completely different property of penetrating radiation. In medical diagnostics X-rays photons of energies of about 100 eV are used to obtain radiographs, i.e. "photographs" of internal organs. Biological tissues are opaque to X-rays, that is, they absorb them more or less intensely depending on their composition. When they cross the material, the X-rays undergo an attenuation that depends on the thickness and the specific weight of the material crossed, the greater the thickness and the specific weight, the larger the attenuation. However, X-rays have a limited path and are able to pass through only a few tens of centimeters of concrete without being absorbed. Very different is the muography. The muons, from which the term muography, are generated by energetic particles (Cosmic Rays) that come from deep space and continuously bombard the earth. These particles, interacting with the atoms of the atmosphere, produce a rain of other particles, among which the pions, which decay very quickly in muons. The muons reach the earth's surface through a flow of penetrating charge radiation which, at sea level, is equal to about 1 muon cm^2/min with an average energy of 2 GeV. Even if about 207 times the mass of the electron and therefore more penetrating, the muons also lose energy when they cross the material with a reduction of the flow that depends on the thickness and density of the material crossed. The muons can however be used to

obtain information on the distribution of densities within massive structures with densities that do not exceed the density of 1 km of equivalent rock. Therefore, by measuring the absorption of muons in the massive structure, we can trace the density distribution inside (density structure), recognizing voids and / or zones with anomalous characteristics. The term muography is often accompanied by the term muonic tomography. It is easy to realize that if several instruments observe the same object from different angles, a 3D image will be obtained by combining the observations of each instrument. Obviously the tomography would be able to solve with greater detail the geometric details of the voids / areas of the massive internal structure. The possibility of obtaining high resolution and high signal-to-noise muographies of Teide with the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY, possibly complemented with a few additional telescopes installed closer to the volcano cone is very attractive. In particular, the crater of the Teide is currently the preferential way of ascent of hydrothermal fluids and it is probable that there is a central area ad high permeability and very likely lower density than the surrounding ones. This makes the Teidea scientific target particularly interesting for new technology. It should be noted that an experiment was already carried out in 2014 in Teide with classical previous muon tomography approach, by a team of Spanish and Japanese scientists, with interesting but still not definitive results. The new approach to be carried out with the ASTRI telescopes will be able to provide more detailed information on the internal structure of a volcano.

3. Technical Overview

The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY SST structures are based on the modified Schwarzschild – Couder design for the Imaging Atmospheric Cherenkov Telescopes (IACT) [4]. The telescope has a primary mirror diameter of 4.3 m, a primary-to-secondary distance of 3 m and a distance from the camera to the secondary mirror of 0.52 m. It adopts an altitude-azimuthal design in which the azimuth axis permits a rotation range of $\pm 270^\circ$. The mirror dish is mounted on the azimuth fork, which allows rotation around the elevation axis from -1° to $+90^\circ$. The mast structure that supports the secondary mirror and the camera is fixed on the mirror dish. The resulting mechanical structure has a weight of 16 tons but is also very stiff that in turns has proven advantageous (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Left: 3D model of the opto-mechanical structure. Right: main parameters of primary and secondary mirrors.

Eighteen hexagonal panels make-up the primary mirror (M1) of the telescope. In order to reproduce the aspherical optical profile of M1, its surface is arranged in three concentric rings each built from mirror segments with different profiles. The result is that the M1 behaves like a monolithic mirror. The M2 mirror is instead a monolithic substrate thick glass shell of 19 mm thickness and 1.8 m diameter bent to the desired radius of curvature. The resulting optical system has a plate scale of 37.5 mm/°, an angular pixel size $\leq 0.19^\circ$, and an equivalent focal length of 2150 mm. This setup delivers a corrected field of view (FoV) up to 10.5° in diameter and a mean value of the effective area of about 6 m², ensuring that more than 80% of the light emitted by a point source is collected within the dimensions of a Cherenkov camera pixel over the full FoV of the telescope.

The implementation of the 2M design for an IACT telescope is a new concept. Proven technology is used where possible and through the ASTRI prototype the 2M concept has been proven.

The telescope has an alt-azimuthal mount with standard azimuth and elevation drive solutions.

The primary mirror segments are produced using the cold slumping process in which a thin sheet of glass is formed at room temperature over a mould. The mirrors have a sandwich-like structure, with a density of about 15 kg/m² resulting in very light mirrors so that handling and mounting operations are easy.

The large size (almost 2 m diameter) aspherical secondary mirror could not be produced using the cold slumping technique because of the dimensions and of the steep sag profile required. The technique used is the indirect hot slumping where a thin and flat slab of glass is positioned above a mould with the shape profile of the desired optical surface and by means of a thermal cycle in an oven, that changes the viscosity properties of the glass, it adheres and slumps onto the mould surface and assumes the shape of the mould.

The coating that will be used is made by Al+SiO₂+ZrO₂, and has been fully tested with respect to CTA requirements.

ASTRI prototype has an innovative modular focal plane camera with silicon photo-multipliers and a logical pixel size of 6.2mm x 6.2mm, a wide-field-of-view (9.6 degrees in diameter), and an energy sensitive in the band of few TeV up to few hundreds TeV (Figure 5).

Figure 5: ASTRI Camera (design and prototype).

The purpose of the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY as a pathfinder in the early phase of CTA will be manifold:

- Assessment of array trigger;
- Testing of array control software and general operation testing ;
- Testing AIV procedures on site (time, personnel, infrastructure, tools) ;
- Testing array performance against Montecarlo simulations;
- Testing the implementation of the intensity interferometry capability.

Compared to currently operating IACT systems, the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY will extend the sensitivity up to 100 TeV and beyond, an almost unexplored energy range by IACTs (Figure 3). Moreover, it will benefit from a much larger field of view, which will allow us to monitor simultaneously a few close-by sources during the same pointing. The combination of the sensitivity extended to 100 TeV and of the homogeneous performance across the FOV will allow us to study emission from extended sources like supernova remnants (SNRs) and pulsar wind nebulae (PWN) at $E > 10$ TeV, and to investigate the presence of spectral cut-offs at energies never observed.

The use of a SiPMs-based camera will improve the duty cycle of the system allowing safe and effective operation with any level of moon condition. The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY will be able to perform astronomical observations with a great energy resolution (about 10–15 %). Moreover, solid Monte Carlo simulations yield an improvement in sensitivity that, for nine telescopes, could greatly surpass the H.E.S.S. sensitivity above 10 TeV, extending up to about 100 TeV. Thus, the ASTRI mini-array can be seen as a “building block” for the full SST array of CTA.

It will provide a full functional complement of MAGIC and CTA North (which lacks of the Small Size Telescopes and, for this reason, has just a limited sensitivity at very high gamma-ray energies) ([5] and references therein).

4. Technology Drivers

For 50 years, ground-based γ -ray telescopes have successfully used single, tessellated mirror-surface designs. Designs of this type have been prototyped for all three sizes of CTA telescope.

The evolving scientific needs of the field motivated a search for a new design that features both better angular resolution and a wider field of view (FoV). Better angular resolution translates directly into better sensitivity to point sources, which are generally studied in the regime limited by the background from charged cosmic rays. It also enables the mapping of spatially-extended sources in sharper detail, ultimately enabling improved morphological studies important to understanding the particle acceleration processes involved. A wider FoV also improves the efficiency of survey observations and the response to transient events that are not well localized. It increases the effective collection area of the telescope as well, by enabling the detection of showers at larger impact parameter and reducing the cases of large-image camera truncation.

The angular resolution of current IACT arrays is still far from the intrinsic limit of the technique that is determined by shower fluctuations. It can be substantially improved for large arrays of IACTs if the camera pixels can be reduced below the current size ($\sim 0.15^\circ$), and if the image quality of the telescope optical system can be correspondingly improved; the pixel size is matched to the optical point-spread function (PSF) for cost optimization. Ideally, the pixel resolution should match (or oversample) the transverse size of the central region of the cascade, typically spanning a few minutes of arc.

Improving the camera resolution while at the same time increasing its FoV is problematic for existing IACT designs. A telescope with prime-focus optics has chromatic aberrations which can be reduced only by increasing the focal length. This, in turn, increases the plate scale and therefore the physical size of the individual pixels of a given angular size in the camera. The resulting telescope's cost can then be dominated by expensive large-aperture photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). The ASTRI SST team, of which Brazil is also participating (see Section 5), has been pioneering a new design which overcomes these limitations by constructing a dual-mirror system (see Section 3, [4]). This optical design, a Schwarzschild-Couder Telescope (SCT), largely cancels aberrations and demagnify the images. The same principle is being also used in the construction of an MST prototype by USA and other partners within the CTA (the so called SCT).

In summary, the advantage of the 2M design is that it allows us to correct, at the same time, spherical, coma and astigmatism aberrations over a large FoV. A secondary mirror decreases the effective focal length resulting in a plate scale that enables the

use of a compact telescope and camera with a physical pixel size compatible with COTS sensors used in medical applications.

5. Organization, Partnerships, and Current Status

The ASTRI Team is made up of staff from various INAF Institutes and Italian Universities; IAG-USP, EACH-USP, and UnicSul in Brazil; and the North West University of South Africa.

The Brazilian members started in the ASTRI Project in 2014 within the CTA Consortium. In the framework of the FAPESP Thematic Project 13/10559-5, the SST-BR party of IAG-USP and associated partners obtained funding to participate in the construction of the ASTRI prototype for CTA, and the MINI-ARRAY. The SST-BR group is funding three of the nine MINI-ARRAY structures; South Africa part of one (1) of the structures; and Italy the remaining telescopes of the array. The total amount obtained from FAPESP for this thematic project is 12.200.000,00 Reais. Further actions and proposals for raising more funding for the construction phase of the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY and maintenance are in course.

Currently there are 23 Brazilian members in the ASTRI Project. Two Brazilian engineers have been involved in the development of the ASTRI prototype as well as with the construction of the ASTRI camera, and they must continue their activities in Italy, in order to participate of the final testing of the telescope with the camera and acquire the entire knowhow for future manufacturing in Brazil of other SST telescopes for the CTA-South Array.

Recently, the CTAO has chosen the ASTRI (among other 2 prototypes) to be the structure that will compose all the 70 SST telescopes of the CTA observatory. The ASTRI team is also developing a full program to produce at least 50 SSTs for the CTA first phase (see CTA WP, de Gouveia Dal Pino et al. 2019).

The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY deployment in the site of Tenerife is being led by INAF. Brazilian participation in this construction phase is focussed on the exchange of students and engineers, and the development of the Science case. A new proposal is in preparation in this regard.

An MOU between USP and INAF for the use of the ASTRI MINI-ARRAY has been signed in 2015.

6. Schedule

Within the framework of the ASTRI Project, the SST prototype was inaugurated in Sicily in 2014 and is now operational, after extensive testing. Testing and reassessment have been performed with this original prototype since 2014 and a new structure design has

been developed (Figure 2). The first of the nine telescopes of the MINI-ARRAY has been just manufactured based on this new model. This structure has been funded with resources of our FAPESP Thematic Project 13/10559-5 (see Sect. 5). The other two structures supported by us will be soon manufactured.

The ASTRI MINI-ARRAY is under advanced development and site implementation. We expect to perform the complete commissioning during 2020 year, in order to start carrying out the scientific verification phase in 2021 and then making scientific observations in 2022.

Work on the infrastructure, including telescope foundations, is planned to begin in 2020. The first telescopes are expected to be on site in 2020. The completion of telescopes installation is expected to be around 2022.

The Key Science Program for the first years of operation, as discussed in Sec. 2, is in preparation. Monte Carlo simulations of the array configuration are in preparation (see Figure 2).

7. Cost

ASTRI MINI-ARRAY as a whole is a middle, ground-based project. A cost estimate value for an SST Telescope is ~ 1.16 M€ (including a 10% contingency). This breaks down to: ~ 0.92 M€ and ~ 0.23 M€ for the structure and camera respectively (including their respective on-site AIV costs). The on-site AIV cost represents ~ 0.25 M€ of the total Telescope cost.

References

- [1] Acharya B.S., et al. (2013). Introducing the CTA Concept. *Astroparticle Physics*, 43, 3. (This is the lead article in a special volume of *Astroparticle Physics* dedicated to science with CTA.)
- [2] CTA White Paper (2019), de Gouveia Dal Pino E.M. et al (2019)
- [3] Acharya B.S., et al. (2019). Science with the Cherenkov Telescope Array. World Scientific, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1142/10986>
- [4] Vassiliev V. V. and Fegan S. J. (2008). Schwarzschild-Couder two-mirror telescope for ground-based gamma-ray astronomy. *Proceedings of the 30th ICRC (Merida)*, 1445; arXiv:0708.2741
- [5] Lombardi, S. et al. (2019), First detection of the Crab Nebula at TeV energies with a Cherenkov telescope in dual-mirror Schwarzschild-Couder configuration: the ASTRI-Horn telescope, *A&A* submitted, eprint arXiv:1909.12149

